

PreMETS

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

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D2.1 Future Employee Profile

Final

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1. INTRODUCTION

The general objectives of PreMETS are to introduce an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training for the development of a coherent digital platform that covers all aspects of the PM training process:

- Fostering new, innovative and multidisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning in the field of PM by introducing an innovatively co-created PM curriculum (covering green, digital, entrepreneurial and resilience skills for PM) complemented by innovative teaching methods (i.e. EIT Manufacturing's Teaching Factory Concept), micro-credential certification and bespoke digital learning and co-creation platform for upskilling the current and future PM workforce and tackling skill gaps and mis-matches via skill forecasting and policy making.
- Helping PM companies and related service provider SMEs achieve corporate social responsibility by directly impacting on reducing environmental damage, diminishing social and societal risks and boosting their revenues.
- Stimulating a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial attitudes with regards to achieving resilient PM solutions, mind-sets and skills in adult, vocational and higher education learners.
- Facilitating the flow and co-creation of PM knowledge between higher education, VET actors, research, the public sector and the business sector in the field of PM in order to jointly contribute to upskilling and regional economic growth by developing capacities and clusters in the field of PM.
- Building and supporting effective and efficient PM higher education and vocational education and training systems delivered via a joint digital platform, which enables connectivity and inclusivity, contributing to innovation and equal access to high quality education for all in the emerging work field of PM.

To ensure that the training needs of both future employee in PM and future trainers in PM are fully reflected in the educational content, PreMETS adopts an innovative approach as a starting point of its methodological development by relying on OECD's strategic foresight approach. The futuring/foresight process is linked with the pre-identified training needs for PM workforce and PM trainer needs. After the foresight is finalized, the learner & trainer profiles will be based on use-case approaches. This will feed into better shaping the training content (i.e. the PM toolkit), while also will enable a better integration with EU's ESCO system.

In this context, this document introduces a brief methodology for undertaking the foresight exercises complemented by an integrated followup and result from the foresight exercise undertaken by the consortium. This followup comprises of the outcomes upon which the future Employee and Trainer profiles have been created under several scenarios (use cases).

1.1 Foresight workshop overview

In an ever-changing world where uncertainty is the new normal, organizations must embrace a proactive approach to stay ahead of the curve. Foresight workshops have emerged as a powerful tool for anticipating and preparing for potential future challenges and opportunities. These workshops bring together diverse perspectives, analytical tools, and creative thinking to foster strategic planning based on informed foresight. This page delves into the concept of foresight workshops, their importance, and the benefits they offer to organizations seeking to navigate an unpredictable future.

What are Foresight Workshops?

Foresight workshops are collaborative sessions designed to explore potential future scenarios, identify emerging trends, and assess their implications for an organization's strategic decision-making. These workshops bring together stakeholders from different backgrounds, including experts, executives, employees, and external partners, to collectively envision possible futures and develop strategies to cope with various outcomes.

The Process of Foresight Workshops:

- **Environmental Scanning:** Participants gather data and insights from various sources, such as trend analysis, market research, and technological advancements, to understand the current landscape.
- **Scenario Building:** Different plausible future scenarios are constructed, each representing a unique set of circumstances and challenges that might unfold. These scenarios often encompass a range of possibilities, from the most optimistic to the most pessimistic.
- **Systematic Analysis:** Each scenario is rigorously analyzed to understand its potential impact on the organization, including risks, opportunities, and required adaptations.
- **Strategic Planning:** Based on the insights gained from scenario analysis, participants develop strategic plans and adaptive measures to be implemented in response to the potential scenarios.
- **Actionable Roadmaps:** The outcomes of the workshop are translated into practical roadmaps that guide the organization in the face of future uncertainties.

The Importance of Foresight Workshops

- **Risk Mitigation:** Foresight workshops help organizations identify potential risks and vulnerabilities in advance, enabling them to take proactive measures to mitigate their impact.
- **Opportunity Exploration:** By exploring various future scenarios, organizations can uncover new opportunities and competitive advantages that might otherwise remain hidden.
- **Adaptation and Resilience:** With a better understanding of potential challenges, organizations can develop adaptive strategies to remain resilient in the face of changing circumstances.
- **Strategic Decision-Making:** Foresight workshops equip decision-makers with well-informed insights, reducing the reliance on reactive decision-making and improving long-term planning.
- **Innovation and Creativity:** These workshops encourage innovative thinking and creativity, fostering an organizational culture that values anticipation and preparedness.

Benefits of Foresight Workshops:

- Enhanced Strategic Planning: Organizations can develop robust strategic plans that account for a wide range of possibilities and uncertainties.
- Future-Proofing: By actively engaging in foresight, organizations become more agile and future-proof, allowing them to stay ahead of competitors and changes in the market.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Foresight workshops promote cross-functional collaboration and stakeholder engagement, breaking down silos and fostering a shared vision.
- Building a Learning Organization: Through the foresight process, organizations develop a learning-oriented culture that continuously scans the environment for potential shifts.
- Improved Decision-Making: Informed by foresight analysis, decision-making becomes more data-driven and evidence-based, reducing the reliance on gut feelings or short-term perspectives.

Therefore, foresight workshops offer a proactive and strategic approach to address the uncertainty of the future. By engaging in collaborative scenario building and analysis, organizations can uncover insights, embrace opportunities, and fortify themselves against potential threats. With the power of anticipation and informed decision-making, organizations are better equipped to navigate the complexities of an ever-evolving world and ensure long-term success.

1.2 Predictive maintenance employee profile

Format: 1 - 1.5h workshop organised by different partners in different countries.

Step 0:

- Confirm minimum 5 participants for the workshop (can be in person or online). The participants should be diverse (they can be internal as well as external) and should cover expertise tangent to PM needs. Thus they can be industrial experts, academics, employees, technology providers, public authorities, etc.
- During the event and/or before, ask the to sign the consent form (see Appendix)
- Inform them that photos will be taken (and take some photos/screenshots).
- Workshops should be finalised by 15th September !

Step 1: Starting point of the workshop, initiate a discussion:

- Present briefly PreMETS
- How will industrial systems look like in 10 years (focus on the roles of humans vs technology) ?
- What will be the external pressures ? (social, environmental, regulatory)
- What new technologies will emerge and how will they impact on the industrial systems ?

Step 2: “Dream” – imagine the ideal scenario in 10 years from now, how would (ideally/utopic) the PM job profile look like, what would people do, know and benefit from ? During the workshop fill in this table (moderator), the idea is to look at each skill, discuss its probability and maybe remove/add new one.

Table 3.1 – Idealistic/Utopic scenario – Employee Profile Use Case

Skill	Pressures that enable/push it	Technologies that enable/push it	Barriers
<p>WN1: Holistic PM competences – Sensing technologies, Maintenance methodologies, Time Management systems, Reporting models, Structural Assessment methods, Forecasting systems, Remote infrastructure management</p>	<p>Pressures Enabling Predictive Maintenance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost-effective and Human-Centred Maintenance. • Data science and analytics skills. • Well-educated in ML and AI techniques. <p>Future Predictive Maintenance Landscape:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological advances, cost-saving imperatives, and data-driven decision-making. • Adherence to stricter environmental regulations. • Proficiency in managing assets remotely. <p>Cross-Disciplinary Knowledge and Expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep understanding of data science, artificial intelligence, IoT, AIoT, 	<p>Technologies Enabling Predictive Maintenance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IoT and AI. • IoT, ML, and AI. <p>High-Tech Tools for Predictive Maintenance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors and IoT devices provide real-time machine data. • AI-powered programs predict potential breakdowns. • Big data tools analyze data for critical insights. • Cloud computing ensures smooth operations. • 5G networks enable remote machine monitoring. • AR and VR enhance visualization. • Blockchain ensures data integrity. <p>Empowering Technologies for PM Models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI and machine learning. • Advanced sensors and IoT. 	<p>Challenges in Predictive Maintenance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of industrial datasets. • Limited employee knowledge. • Lack of regulatory compliances. • Initial investment costs. <p>Potential Challenges in Technology Adoption:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity threats and vulnerabilities due to interconnected devices. • Managing and analyzing a vast amount of data from sensors, AI, and IoT. • Keeping up with the latest tools and methodologies. • Ethical considerations, such as bias in algorithms or job displacement. <p>Barriers Related to Specific Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of physics regarding sensors and quantum computers. • Regulatory barriers related to AI. • Lack of integration of data analysis with mechanical engineering projects in university courses. <p>Technical Expertise Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thorough knowledge of monitoring systems required for effective PM. • Operators' inability to interpret and use data for machinery maintenance.

	<p>engineering, and sustainability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to tackle complex problems from various angles. <p>Time Management and Forecasting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transition to prescriptive maintenance. • Advanced sensor-based self-assessment. • Less reliance on manual reporting. <p>Maintenance Methodologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evolving methodologies based on sensor data. <p>Sensing Technologies and Data Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding sensor installation and data analysis. <p>Remote Infrastructure Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills for real-time remote asset management. <p>Data Visualization Models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced data interaction for end-users. <p>Changing Maintenance Costs and Complexity:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital twins for real-time system monitoring. • Augmented reality and virtual reality. • Blockchain for data integrity. • 5G for remote monitoring. • Drones and robots for inspections. <p>Other Supporting Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New sensors, including virtual ones. • ML technologies for issue categorization. • Open-source software for data consolidation. • Knowledge management platforms. • Easy-to-implement tools and SaaS solutions. <p>Ethical Considerations in Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical AI and responsible innovation. • Secure cybersecurity framework. • Promoting human-AI collaboration. • Leveraging drones for inspections. • Utilizing cloud-based collaboration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and adaptability to different PM roles with varying system complexities. <p>Cultural and Data Management Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural barriers around data perception and storage. • Importance of data collection for components that rarely fail. • Transitioning time between older and advanced systems. • Materials availability for advanced system development. <p>Liability and Responsibility Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining and addressing liability for PM experts. • Better definition of responsibilities in PM implementation. <p>Corporate and Organizational Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change when existing processes work. • Digital twins initiating the maintenance cycle. • Reluctance to share data among corporations. <p>Overall Challenges and Concerns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of implementation. • Compatibility issues with existing systems. • Technological skills gap. • Data privacy concerns. • Ethical and legal concerns. • Cultural resistance to new PM approaches.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emphasis on preventative work.• Automation of maintenance.• Process analysis and understanding. <p>Continuous Technological Advancements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emphasis on safety, quality, and environmental responsibility.• Data-driven decision-making and remote monitoring. <p>Green Skills for Sustainability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Environmental compliance and emissions monitoring.• Eco-friendly logistics and smart tech. <p>Lifecycle Analysis and Resource Efficiency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Knowledge of sustainability impact and compliance. <p>Renewable Energy Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Competencies in sustainable energy use. <p>Environmental, Geo-Political, and Economic Impacts:</p>		
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Linking industrial processes to broader expertise areas. <p>Sustainable Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Expertise in recycling and waste reduction. <p>Communication and Sales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Selling the benefits of sustainable maintenance. <p>Climate Change and Limited Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Addressing environmental challenges. <p>Safety and Security:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensuring human safety and asset security. <p>Resilience Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Mitigation strategies and efficient recovery planning. <p>Forecasting Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Direct machine-provided forecasting. <p>Cybersecurity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensuring data and system security. <p>Market Awareness and Business Trends:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Understanding market dynamics.		
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	<p>Change Management and Innovation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasizing continuous improvement and responsible innovation. <p>Flexibility and Adaptability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embracing change and self-directed learning. <p>Human-Machine Interaction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing communication with AI and robots. <p>Semantics and Special Coordination:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimizing communication with AI. <p>Full Integration of Digital Competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incorporating digital skills into education. 		
<p>WN2: Digital skills competences for PM – Signal and Image Processing, Structural Simulation technics, Big-data analytics, IoT, Artificial Intelligence,</p>	<p>Proficiency in Remote Asset Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> As globalization and remote work continue to rise, the ability to manage assets remotely using cutting-edge technologies becomes 	<p>Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital Twins (DT) Augmented Reality (AR) Mixed Reality Big Data Artificial Intelligence (AI) Natural Language Processing (NLP) 	<p>Competencies and Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of competencies and skills in emerging digital technologies. Ongoing training needs to keep up with evolving technology trends. <p>Digital Ethics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growing concerns about data privacy and security breaches.

<p>Augmented Reality, Remote-Accessed Robotics, Digital Twin.</p>	<p>crucial for success in the field.</p> <p>Cross-Disciplinary Knowledge and Expertise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A deep understanding of various fields, including data science, artificial intelligence, IoT, AIoT, engineering, and sustainability, is essential. Professionals need cross-disciplinary knowledge to address complex problems effectively. <p>Time Management and Forecasting Systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moving towards prescriptive maintenance, embedded sensors and AI enable self-assessment, life cycle prediction, and continuous monitoring of machine status. The focus shifts from manual forecasting to AI-driven insights. <p>Changing Maintenance Methodologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traditional maintenance methodologies will evolve significantly over 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital Security Cyber-Physical Systems <p>Technological Synergy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration with technologies such as IoT, AI, and Big Data Analytics to create a synergistic landscape for optimizing predictive maintenance. <p>Digital Skills Requirement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rapid advancements in technology, including AI, IoT, edge computing, quantum computing, robots, and automation, compel professionals to acquire digital skills for effective PM. <p>Sensor Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilization of sensors with signal and image processing capabilities, computer vision sensors, and audio systems for data collection and analysis in PM. <p>AI and Emissions Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI's role in PM extends to understanding fault and changes in consumption (emissions), particularly relevant in the automotive sector. Predicting consumption emissions may 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Necessity for digital skills in cybersecurity and secure data handling for PM. <p>Cultural and Educational Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need to educate entrepreneurs and society about the transformation of physical work into cognitive and engineering work. Schools must prepare students for technical and future jobs in the evolving landscape. <p>Time and Connectivity Issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time pressure and the need to ensure connectivity in an automated environment. Balancing the role of machines and manual maintenance, and addressing data safety and sovereignty concerns. <p>Additional Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of awareness and education about the changing PM landscape. Skills gap in coping with technological complexity. Limited access to resources for acquiring necessary skills. Data management challenges in handling PM-related data securely.
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	<p>the next decade, driven by sensor technology and data analysis applied to specific systems.</p> <p>Sensor Technology and Data Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Proficiency in sensor installation, performance evaluation, and data analysis is critical for ensuring accurate predictive maintenance. <p>Time Management System Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Understanding and managing machine usage time, predicting downtime, and resource allocation will remain essential skills. The organization of PM will be increasingly system-led. <p>Reporting Models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reporting models will mainly be relevant for extraordinary maintenance or impactful anomalies, as AI systems will handle routine reporting. <p>Remote Infrastructure Management:</p>	<p>become part of PM in the future.</p> <p>Integration and Data Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integration of AI into PM processes.• Utilization of data clouds to combine process information across different companies.• Easy access to advanced digital learning opportunities for skill development. <p>Key Digital Competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Advanced Signal and Image Processing.• Cutting-Edge Structural Simulation Techniques.• Big Data Analytics and Machine Learning.• Artificial Intelligence for Predictive Maintenance.• Augmented Reality (AR) for Training and Field Work.	
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- Proficiency in remote infrastructure management will be vital for real-time data extraction, analysis, and remote intervention in networks and machinery.

Data Visualization Models:

- Augmented interaction with end-users through advanced touch screens and data visualization models will be necessary for efficient data interpretation.

Emphasis on Preventative Work:

- The rising cost of maintenance emphasizes the importance of preventative work over corrective measures.

Automated Maintenance for Complex Systems:

- High-complexity systems with many interconnected parts will require automated maintenance.

Continuous Technological Advancements:

- A focus on safety, quality, environmental

	<p>responsibility, and a culture of predictive and preventive maintenance will be essential. Decision-making will be data-driven, and remote monitoring and global collaboration will play significant roles in the field.</p>		
<p>WN3: Green skills competences for PM – ESG compliance, Emissions evaluation, Lifecycle analysis, Resource Efficiency, Consumption optimization, Renewable Energy Sources, Green Urban Logistics, in blend with GreenComp competences.</p>	<p>Effective Human-in-the-Loop Processes in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding signals and images from machines to predict issues. • Using computer simulations to understand how structures like buildings and equipment behave. • Leveraging big-data skills to uncover hidden insights from large volumes of information. • Utilizing IoT and AI to monitor machines in real-time and predict potential issues. • Augmented Reality (AR) simplifies visualization. 	<p>Green Skills Enabled by Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generative Product Design • Materials Selection and Traceability • Use of Novel Eco-Friendly Materials in Production • Utilization of Renewable Energy Sources <p>Technology-Enabled Green Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) Compliance benefits from Data Analytics. • Emissions Evaluation relies on Sensors and IoT (Internet of Things). • Lifecycle Analysis uses Advanced Software. • Resource Efficiency and Consumption Optimization leverage IoT and AI (Artificial Intelligence). 	<p>Challenges Related to Green Practices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Skills in Green Practices • Environmental Compliance and Regulations <p>Implementation Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited Expertise in Implementing Green Practices • Managers of Cloud Computing need to consider environmental regulations. • Tension between Sustainability and the Economy: Longer product lifespan conflicts with economic interests. • Continuous Technological Advancements lead to an ongoing need for training. • Variations in Environmental Policies in different countries or regions. • Data Ownership throughout the Product Life Cycle. • Resolution of Energy and Raw Material Issues, reducing the need for conservation or limitations. <p>Key Challenges:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Remote-controlled robots and Digital Twins enable remote management of machines. <p>Digital Skills and Competencies for PM Professionals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Proficiency in data analysis with semi-revised algorithms to understand advanced sensors.• Competence in managing data security in the era of vast and heterogeneous data.• UX/UI Design skills for designing user-friendly interfaces.• Expertise in data science and software development for analyzing machine-generated signals.• Understanding of IoT technologies, which are crucial soft skills for the manufacturing industry.• Utilization of augmented reality and Digital Twins for simulating and	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integration of Renewable Energy Sources via Smart Grids.• Green Urban Logistics Optimization with IoT and AI.• GreenComp Competences rely on Digital Platforms and Data Analytics to ensure eco-friendly maintenance practices. <p>Relevance to Steel Manufacturing and Similar Sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Utilization of Data Clouds to provide information about raw materials in all stages of the manufacturing process.• Implementation of Quality Management Data (Scrap, Defects) for better product quality control. <p>Key Technological Tools and Platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) Compliance Platforms.• Emissions Monitoring and Evaluation Tools.• Resource Efficiency Optimization Software.• Lifecycle Analysis Software.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Regulatory Complexity• Limited Access to Green Resources• Resistance to Sustainable Practices
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	<p>understanding system behaviors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embracing digitalization of work processes and enhancing digital literacy. <p>Key Focus Areas in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasis on technological advancements. Ensuring quality and safety. Achieving efficiency and cost reduction. Data-driven decision-making. Implementing proactive maintenance strategies. Real-time monitoring of assets. Enhancing visualization through AR/VR. Enabling remote access and automation in maintenance processes. 		
<p>WN4: Resilience competences for PM – Human Safety systems, Risk Assessment tools, Structural assessment, Mitigation strategies, Forecasting tools,</p>	<p>Need for Green Skills and Competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zero Emissions Vision Circular Economy Vision Energy Efficiency Optimization Techniques 	<p>Ensuring Human Safety with Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human-Robot Collaboration IoT and Machine Learning/AI Safety Systems Utilizing Smart Sensors 	<p>Challenges in Competencies and Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of Competencies and Skills Business Continuity Planning Increasing Complexity of Advanced PM Technologies Steep Learning Curve Skills Gap

<p>Efficient Recovery planning.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular Economy Techniques <p>Drivers for Green Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Compliance (ESG) • Emissions Monitoring • Efficient Resource Use • Shift to Renewable Energy Sources • Urbanization and Eco-Friendly Logistics <p>Essential Competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Technology (GreenComp) for Environmentally Conscious Maintenance • Lifecycle Analysis Knowledge • Resource Efficiency Expertise • Competence in Renewable Energy Sources <p>Environmental Considerations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding Environmental, Geo-Political, and Economic Impacts • Sustainable Management (Eco-Design and Green Building) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Assessment Tools with Advanced Analytics • Structural Assessment with Sensor Technology • High-Tech Mitigation Strategies with IoT • AI and Machine Learning-Powered Forecasting Tools • Digital Platforms for Efficient Recovery Planning <p>Resilience Competencies in Advanced PM Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing Complexity of PM Technologies • Troubleshooting Complex Maintenance Ecosystems • Addressing Growing Cybersecurity Threats and Vulnerabilities • Protecting Maintenance Data and Systems from Attacks <p>Applications of Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous Vehicles • AI Integration • Big Data Analytics • Automated Medical Scanning and Health Predictability • Technologies Supporting Human Movements (e.g., lifting and carrying) <p>Key Technological Tools and Systems:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration Challenges with Various PM and Resilience Technologies • Interoperability Challenges <p>Data Access and Security:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limitation of Data Access • Emphasis on Data Security • Complexity in Data Access and Exchanges • Preventing Unauthorized Data Access <p>Other Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource Limitations • Cultural Barriers • Lack of Recovery Planning • Resistance to Structural Assessment • Emergence of Human-Free Factories
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Communication and Sales Skills for Promoting Sustainable PM <p>External Factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Climate Change• Limited Resources• Changing Policies• Building Partner and Expert Networks <p>Key Factors for Achieving Green Competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Global Sustainability Commitment• Integrated ESG Culture• Environmental Transparency• Adoption of Advanced Green Technologies• Collaborative Research Initiatives• Embracing Holistic Sustainability Metrics• Cultivating a Culture of Continuous Improvement• Providing Incentives for Green Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Safety Systems and Wearables• Risk Assessment Software• Structural Assessment Tools• Mitigation Strategy Planning Software	
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<p>WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM – Opportunity detection mindset, innovative solution identification, Team management, entrepreneurial decision making, launching new services/products, responsible innovation, customer service & communication, in blend with EntreComp competences.</p>	<p>Skills and Competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety and Security in the Factory • Industry 5.0 Vision • Remote Monitoring and Diagnostics • Resilience Skills on the Rise • Risk Assessment and Mitigation • Structural Integrity Assurance • Efficient Recovery Planning • Forecasting and Adverse Event Preparation • Adaptation to Economic Uncertainties • Addressing Emerging Risks and Threats • Cybersecurity for Product and Data Safety • Protection of Labor Laws • Empowerment of Security and Environmental Specialists • Changing Policies for Continuous Risk Assessment • Reducing Quality Issues and Downtime <p>Considerations:</p>	<p>Cloud/Edge Computing and On-Demand Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Data Analytics and AI for Opportunity Detection • Digital Platforms for Streamlined Team Management • Launching New Services or Products Based on Customer Feedback • Empowering EntreComp Competences • Exploring New Business Models • Leveraging Intrapreneurship Initiatives • Utilizing Idea Management Systems <p>Advanced Technologies and Automation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of Robots, 3D Printing, 5G, IoT & AIoT, AI, etc. • Exploring New Business Models • Digital Collaboration Tools and Ecosystems • Creation of Disruptive Solutions • Contribution to the Evolution of Maintenance Practices <p>Tools and Competencies:</p>	<p>Lack of Validated Business Models and Solution Validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty in the Value Chain • Ensuring PM Solutions Meet Customer Needs • Market Viability of PM Solutions <p>Resistance to Change and Competitive Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational Resistance to Adoption • Competitive Dynamics in the Market <p>General Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological Complexities (e.g., AI, IoT, Blockchain, Automation) • Skills Shortages in Advanced Technologies and Entrepreneurship • Balancing Short-Term and Long-Term Development • Financial Costs of PM Implementation <p>Existing Initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of Innovation Managers
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human Safety as a Top Priority • Holistic Risk Management Culture • Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration • Ethical Considerations • Crisis Preparedness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idea Generation Platforms • Innovation Management Software • Collaboration and Communication Tools • Data Analytics for Market Research • Prototyping and 3D Printing 	
<p>WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment for PM - Technology adoption readiness, Behavioural adaptation inclination, in blend with DigComp and DigCompEdu competences.</p>	<p>Need for New Business Models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constant Search for Process Improvements • Entrepreneurial Mindset and Leadership • Responsible Innovation and Ethical Practices <p>Innovation Culture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on Continuous Improvement • Market Dynamism and Competitiveness • Technological Advancements • Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration • Customer-Centric Focus • Support for Startups <p>Digital Competencies and Continuous Learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Readiness to Adopt New Technology 	<p>Integration Technologies for Learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-Learning Platforms • Online Learning Communities • Adaptive Learning Platforms <p>Continuous Learning in the Digital World:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitated by Technology • Readiness to Adopt New Tools and Platforms • Behavioral Adaptation Supported by User-Friendly Interfaces • Integration of DigComp and DigCompEdu Competences • Empowerment for Ongoing Education and Skill Development <p>AI in Continuous Learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leveraging AI for Learning Enhancement 	<p>Challenges Due to Lack of Digital Maturity and Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Literacy Gaps • Resistance to Digital Learning • Technological Barriers • Lack of Training <p>Cybersecurity Concerns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for Cybersecurity Skills • Ensuring Data and Systems Security in PM <p>Challenges with Digital Learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to Digital Learning • Limited Access to Resources • Overwhelming Variety of Resources <p>Skills and Competences Gap:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Analysis and Dialectics • Need for Non-STEM Skills and Competences • Emphasis on Communication, Semiotics, Linguistics, Semantics, etc. <p>Resistance to Technological Change:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance from PM Workers • Resistance from PM Trainers • Changes in Role Due to AR/VR Technologies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-Directed Learning and Adaptability • Virtual Collaboration Skills • Effective Communication • Human-Machine Interaction Skills • Semantics and Questioning Skills • Special Coordination in Virtual Environments • Full Integration of Digital Competencies in Education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for DigComp Certification • Improved and Perfected User Experience (UX) <p>Key Learning Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Learning Management Systems (LMS) • Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) Learning • Mobile Learning Apps • AI-Enhanced Learning Platforms • Collaborative Learning Tools 	
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Step 3: “Get down to earth” – imagine the realistic scenario in 10 years from now, how would realistically the PM job profile look like, what would people do, know and benefit from? During the workshop fill in this table (moderator), the idea is to look at each skill, discuss its probability and maybe remove/add new ones.

Table 3.2 – Realistic scenario - Employee Profile Use Case

Skill	Pressures that enable/push it	Technologies that enable/push it	Barriers
WN1: Holistic PM competences – Sensoring technologies, Maintenance	Benefits of Improved Maintenance Management and Predictive Maintenance:	Key Technologies Driving Holistic Predictive Maintenance: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IoT (Internet of Things) 	Challenges: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Adequate Datasets • Inadequate Digital Maturity

<p>methodologies, Time Management systems, Reporting models, Structural Assessment methods, Forecasting systems, Remote infrastructure management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost Reduction • Regulatory Compliance • Competitive Advantage • Environmental Responsibility <p>Key Skills for PM Professionals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialized Engineering Background (Mechanical, Electrical, Industrial, Material Science) • Data Visualisation Models (3D Graphics for Data Communication) • Mechanical and Electrical Skills (Intervention and Maintenance) • Regulatory Compliance Expertise • Time Management Skills • Data Reporting and Analysis • Structural Assessment • Remote Infrastructure Management • Resource Optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI (Artificial Intelligence) • ML (Machine Learning) • Advanced Sensors • Big Data Analytics • Cloud Computing <p>Skills and Expertise Required for PM Professionals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Analytics • Machine Learning • Web and Remote Controlling • Signal Processing • IoT (Internet of Things) and AIoT (AI of Things) • Vibrational and Acoustic Sensors • Online Learning Platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological Maturity • High Initial Investment Costs • Resistance to Change • Limited Human Resources with Cross-Disciplinary Skills • Complexity of Technologies' Communication • Universities and Companies Focusing on Theoretical PM Over Physical Intervention Competences • Potential Job Impact of AI-Driven Approaches • Sensor Errors • Intransparencies Within Companies • Issues with Internal Communication • External Service Providers Taking Over PM Roles
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<p>WN2: Digital skills competences for PM – Signal and Image Processing, Structural Simulation technics, Big-data analytics, IoT, Artificial Intelligence, Augmented Reality, Remote-Accessed Robotics, Digital Twin.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies Embracing Digital Skills for Predictive Maintenance to Save Time and Money • Efficiency and Competitiveness Through IoT, AI, and Augmented Reality • Regulatory Compliance and Safety Concerns Driving Digital Skills Adoption • Increasing Digitalization and Technology Adoption Creating Pressure • Future PM Workforce Requires Strong Programming Skills • Limited Familiarity with Digital Twins Among PM Experts • Augmented Reality Viewed as a Training Tool • Importance of Integrating Digital 	<p>Key Digital Skills and Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Skills for PM Include Signal and Image Processing, Structural Simulation, Big Data Analytics, IoT, AI, Augmented Reality, Remote-Accessed Robotics, and Digital Twins • AI and Machine Learning Knowledge Will Be Integral to the PM Job Profile • IoT, AIoT, VR Glasses, and Signal Processing Are of High Importance • Big Data and IoT Platforms Play a Critical Role • Emphasis on Digital Learning Initiatives with Low Entry-Barrier • Focus on Customized Training and Education Platforms • Promoting Global Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing • Continuous Skill Development and Upkeep • Adherence to Data Security and Privacy Standards 	<p>Challenges and Concerns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Competencies and Skills in Cobots and Emerging Technologies • Technological Maturity of Cobots • Ethical Considerations for the Use of Cobots • Ongoing Training Challenges • Data Privacy Concerns • Data Quality and Noisy/Inaccurate Data • Variability of Data • Interoperability Issues Among IoT Devices/Equipment • Scalability of Systems and Obsolescence • Limitations of VR/AR, Including Motion Sickness and Time Usage • Unpredictable AI Decisions and Results • Lack of Awareness and Education • Financial Constraints • Resistance to Change • Cultural and Behavioral Factors • Global Variability • Need for Interdisciplinary Collaboration

	<p>Competencies into School Curricula</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital Literacy Essential for Competitive Employment 		
<p>WN3: Green skills competences for PM – ESG compliance, Emissions evaluation, Lifecycle analysis, Resource Efficiency, Consumption optimization, Renewable Energy Sources, Green Urban Logistics, in blend with GreenComp competences.</p>	<p>Factors for Improving Environmental Performance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued Emphasis on Environmental Issues Stricter ESG Regulations Adoption of Circular Economy Practices Stricter Emission Guidelines CSRD (Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive) and Non-Financial Reporting ESG Compliance Emissions Evaluation Lifecycle Analysis Resource Efficiency Consumption Optimization Renewable Energy Sources Waste Management 	<p>Factors for Lifecycle Assessment, Renewable Energy, and ESG Compliance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehensive ESG Compliance Tools Enhanced Emissions Assessment Technologies Common Green Urban Logistics Solutions Integration with Green Competency Standards Improved Analysis of Emissions and Climate Change Consumption Optimization Algorithms Renewable Energy Integration Green Urban Logistics Platforms Circular Economy Practices 	<p>Factors for Limited Green Product Designs, Lack of Renewable Energy Resources, and Implementation Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost of Sustainable Technologies Lack of Sustainability Education Regulatory Complexity

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Reporting • Continuous Improvement 		
<p>WN4: Resilience competences for PM – Human Safety systems, Risk Assessment tools, Structural assessment, Mitigation strategies, Forecasting tools, Efficient Recovery planning.</p>	<p>Factors for Increasing Safety and Ensuring Regulatory Compliance, Resource Optimization, and Adaptive Maintenance Techniques:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liability and Legal Compliance • Worker Well-being • Industry Reputation • Risk Management • Operational Efficiency • Technological Advances • Market Demands • Health and Safety Culture • Cost Management 	<p>Factors for Trusted AI, Responsible AI, AI Ethics, and Resilience Competences in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictive Analytics • Efficient Recovery Planning Platforms • Digital Twin for Resilience • Real-time Monitoring and Alert Systems • Machine Learning for Risk Mitigation 	<p>Challenges in Lack of Competencies and Skills, Data Security, Resource Constraints, and Disseminating Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of Risk Assessment • Resource Constraints • Lack of Recovery Planning
<p>WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM – Opportunity detection mindset, innovative solution identification, Team management, entrepreneurial decision</p>	<p>Factors for Improving Innovation Capacity, Increasing Revenues, and Creative Problem Solving:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market Competition • Customer Expectations • Changing Regulations • Risk Mitigation 	<p>Factors for Cloud/Edge Computing, Analytics Tools, and DSS in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A culture of opportunity detection • Established innovative solution identification platforms • Effective team management tools 	<p>Factors for Conservatism and Lack of Innovation Culture in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited training in soft skills may foster barriers in innovation & entrepreneurship competences. • The evolution and innovation of the product has the same speed as PM. There is a need for usable results sooner to create a better perception of products.

<p>making, launching new services/products, responsible innovation, customer service & communication, in blend with EntreComp competences.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative Partnerships • Environmental Responsibility • Recognition and Career Growth • Training and Development Programs • Mentorship and Networking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial decision-making support • Accessible launching new services/products platforms • Common customer service & communication platforms • Alignment with EntreComp Competences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant cost for companies, requiring a balance between short-term and long-term development. • Conservative industry practices that resist change and innovation.
<p>WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment for PM - Technology adoption readiness, Behavioural adaptation inclination, in blend with DigComp and DigCompEdu competences.</p>	<p>Factors for Skills Improvement, Training, and Digital Literacy in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The motivation to relearn how to learn in a digital environment for PM arises from the need to embrace technology, adapt behavior, and meet digital competence expectations. • Better implementation of the Digital Competence (DigComp) framework. • Factors driving the need for skills improvement include technological 	<p>Factors for Integration Technologies, e-Learning Platforms, and Technology Adoption Readiness in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of programs for technology adoption readiness, facilitating increased inclination for behavioral adaptation. • Alignment with Digital Competence (DigComp) and DigCompEdu Competences. <p>Technological Tools and Platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamification and Serious Games. • Simulators and Virtual Labs. • Digital Competence Assessment Tools. • Data Analytics for Learning Analytics. 	<p>Factors Related to Technology Evolution and Digital Maturity in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rapid evolution of technology and the need to keep pace with technological advancements. • Concerns about cybersecurity and the protection of digital assets. • The challenge of achieving digital maturity within organizations. • Addressing the digital divide and ensuring equitable access to digital resources. • The need for training in non-STEM disciplines to support human-machine interactions and semantic communication for efficient use of AI. <p>Factors Related to Training and Learning in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital fatigue leading some individuals to prefer traditional learning methods. <p>Data Privacy and Security Concerns:</p>

PreMETS

D2.1 Future Employee Profile

	<p>advancements, industry digitalization, efficiency demands, remote work trends, cybersecurity awareness, and sustainability integration.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• AI Chatbots for Learning Support.• Cybersecurity Training Platforms.• Blockchain for Credentialing: Utilizing blockchain technology for secure and verifiable credentialing of digital competences and certifications.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Concerns about data privacy and the secure handling of data in digital environments.
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2. PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE TRAINER PROFILE

Format: 1 - 1.5h workshop organised by different partners in different countries.

Step 0:

- Confirm minimum 5 participants for the workshop (can be in person or online). The participants should be diverse (they can be internal as well as external) and should cover expertise tangent to PM needs. Thus they can be industrial experts, academics, employees, technology providers, public authorities, coaches/trainers etc.
- During the event and/or before, ask the to sign the consent form (see Appendix)
- Inform them that photos will be taken (and take some photos/screenshots).
- Workshops should be finalised by 15th September !

Step 1: Starting point of the workshop, initiate a discussion:

- Present briefly PreMETS
- How will learning & training (for companies) look like in 10 years (focus on the roles of humans vs technology) ?
- What will be the external pressures ? (social, environmental, regulatory)
- What new technologies will emerge and how will they impact on the learning process ?

Step 2: “Dream” – imagine the ideal scenario in 10 years from now, how would (ideally/utopic) the learning/training in PM (and industry in general) look like, what learners & trainers benefit from (technologically), what would change ? During the workshop fill in this table (moderator), the idea is to look at each skill, discuss its probability and maybe remove/add new ones.

Table 4.1 – Idealistic/Utopic scenario - Trainer Profile Use Case

Skill (ADD/REMOVE for EACH CATEGORY)	Pressures that enable/push it	Technologies that enable/push it	Barriers
<p>TN1: Limited know-how on adopting pedagogical and neuroscience strategies for boosting learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance and successfully embed them in digital formats (for online delivery in higher education and beyond)</p>	<p>Factors Related to Technology Evolution and Digital Maturity in PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rapid evolution of technology and the need to keep pace with technological advancements. • Concerns about cybersecurity and the protection of digital assets. • The challenge of achieving digital maturity within organizations. • Addressing the digital divide and ensuring equitable access to digital resources. • The need for training in non-STEM disciplines to support human-machine interactions and 	<p>Key Elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personalized learning systems tailored to individual needs. • Gamification of virtual learning environments to engage and motivate learners. • Interactive learning methods that encourage active participation. • Case study approaches to provide practical, real-world context for learning. • Offering renowned certificates to validate acquired skills. • Utilization of advanced learning analytics to track and improve learning outcomes. • Implementation of AI-based personalized learning platforms for adaptive training. 	<p>Time resource; Not seen as a priority in management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of time allocated for certain tasks or activities. • Low priority given to certain management tasks. <p>Lack of awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited knowledge or information about a particular subject or issue. <p>Resistance among educators for change and adopting new technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reluctance or opposition among educators to embrace change and use new technologies in their teaching methods. <p>Ruleset and complexity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity arising from rules or regulations. • The presence of intricate rules or systems.

	<p>semantic communication for efficient use of AI.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The impact of digital fatigue, which may lead some individuals to prefer traditional learning methods. • Concerns surrounding data privacy and the secure handling of data in digital environments. 		
<p>TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online higher and vocational education (and beyond) and help educational institutions become more resilient while enabling companies to better motivate employees to engage in constant upskilling</p>	<p>Market competition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased competition in the market or industry. <p>Increased capabilities valued by employers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employers prioritize employees with enhanced skills and abilities. <p>Micro Credentials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of micro-credentials to signify specific skills or accomplishments. <p>Lack of skilled staff should lead to push:</p>	<p>Knowledge Management platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Platforms used for the management of knowledge and information within an organization. <p>Personalized/adaptive learning system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems that tailor educational content and experiences to the individual learner's needs and progress. <p>AI-enabled learning systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning systems integrated with artificial intelligence to enhance the learning experience. <p>Personal complementary AI tutors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-powered tutors that assist learners in their educational journey. <p>Ease of use of the learning platform:</p>	<p>Challenges with Vocational Training Attractiveness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vocational training programs are losing their attractiveness to potential students. • Rapid technological advancements require frequent updates of skills, making it challenging for educators to keep pace. • Developing teaching materials and practical exercises for technical programs is time-consuming. • People often prioritize careers that promise a better quality of life, financial freedom, or require different skills.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The shortage of skilled personnel should motivate efforts or initiatives. <p>Economic competitiveness, need for continuous upskilling, and adaptability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The importance of staying competitive economically, continuously improving skills, and being adaptable to changing circumstances. <p>Higher position offers with financial incentives and status for levels of experts in the field:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Offering higher positions, financial rewards, and elevated status to experts in a particular field. <p>Predictive maintenance jobs will be required in a greater extent than today:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Anticipating an increased demand for predictive	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• User-friendly learning platforms that are easy for both teachers and students to navigate. <p>Interactive teaching/learning technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Technologies that promote active engagement and interaction in the learning process. <p>Information presented in a more digestible way:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Presenting information in a format that is easier to understand and absorb. <p>Enticement with digital awards upon course completion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Providing digital rewards or recognition to learners upon successful completion of a course.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Engineering careers may demand specific skills and a more hands-on approach, which can be less appealing to some individuals.
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	<p>maintenance jobs in the future.</p> <p>Educational institutes will require to work extensively on making education more attractive:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need for educational institutions to make their programs more appealing or enticing. <p>Establishment of well-educated professionals leading society and institutions forward:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The creation of highly educated professionals who play a leading role in advancing society and institutions. 		
<p>TN3: Better foster inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education in online deliveries in higher and vocational education and beyond</p>	<p>Policies to Address Inclusivity and Unique Learning Needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusive policies are crucial in education and workforce development initiatives. Policymakers recognize the 	<p>Accessible Software Integration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessible software is becoming an integral part of all education platforms. Learning analytics tools are used to gather and analyze data on student performance. Predictive learning analytics helps in forecasting student outcomes and 	<p>Ethical Issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different countries and institutions have varying regulations regarding the collection, usage, and analysis of student data, leading to ethical concerns and data privacy issues. Educational institutions need to navigate these regulations to ensure

	<p>importance of addressing the unique learning needs of diverse groups of learners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The global demand for predictive maintenance (PM) jobs is driving the advancement of online education. • The high demand for PM positions necessitates a more inclusive approach to include individuals from various demographic backgrounds. • Trainer skills that can effectively engage a wider range of demographics will be essential to meet the workforce needs. 	<p>adapting teaching methods accordingly.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative creation of teaching materials allows educators to work together in developing resources. • The semantic web is utilized to enhance the organization and retrieval of educational content. <p>Global Networking and High Data Transfer Rates:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global networking applications offer high data transfer rates, facilitating seamless access to educational resources. • These technologies provide easy access to teaching and learning materials. 	<p>compliance and protect students' privacy.</p> <p>Real-Life Experience Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some educational programs require real-life, hands-on experience, which can be challenging to provide in a purely digital or remote learning environment. • Prejudice against careers in engineering or other skill-intensive fields may discourage individuals from pursuing these careers, impacting workforce diversity.
<p>TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections, creation emotional responses to improve learning, and</p>	<p>Rewards for Continuous Education (CE):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies are offering rewards and incentives to employees who 	<p>Gamification and Digital Reward System:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing gamification strategies to make learning engaging and enjoyable. 	<p>Outsourcing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The possibility that certain aspects of predictive maintenance education might be outsourced to external providers or institutions. <p>Ethical Concerns:</p>

<p>understanding timing (for learning content delivery)</p>	<p>engage in continuous education to promote skill development and career growth within the organization.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These rewards can include promotions, salary increases, recognition, or opportunities for career advancement. <p>Growing Popularity of Neuroscience and Cognitive Psychology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neuroscience and cognitive psychology are gaining popularity in the field of education, helping educators understand how the brain learns and retains information. • This knowledge is used to design effective learning experiences that enhance memory, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills. <p>Reinforcing Team Spirit:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilizing digital reward systems to motivate learners and provide recognition for their achievements. <p>UX Improvement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focusing on improving the user experience (UX) of educational platforms to make them more user-friendly and accessible. <p>AI for Personalized Learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) to personalize learning paths and paces based on individual learner needs and preferences. <p>Brain-Computer Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploring brain-computer interfaces to enhance the interaction between learners and educational content, potentially enabling direct communication with learning systems. <p>Virtual Reality for Emotional Engagement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrating virtual reality (VR) to emotionally engage learners in the educational process, creating immersive and memorable learning experiences. <p>Module Interconnection with Augmented Reality (AR):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interconnecting modules with AR applications orchestrated by AI to increase emotional intelligence (EQ) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical considerations surrounding the use of technology, data privacy, and learner well-being in predictive maintenance education. <p>High Costs of Neurotechnology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges associated with the high costs and accessibility of neurotechnology for educational purposes. <p>Complexity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The inherent complexity of predictive maintenance concepts, tools, and technologies that learners must grasp. <p>Reliability and Integration of AR Systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the reliability and seamless integration of augmented reality (AR) systems into educational environments. <p>Underdeveloped Societal Critical Thinking:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need to foster critical thinking skills within society to promote better understanding and decision-making regarding predictive maintenance practices. <p>Student Confusion Regarding Academic and Career Path Choices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing the potential confusion among students when it comes to choosing the right academic and career paths related to predictive maintenance and emerging technologies.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Promoting a culture that merges art with science and encourages a sharing culture within teams.• Emphasizing group responsibilities and collaboration to foster a sense of unity and shared goals. <p>Connectivity Between Knowledge and Application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensuring that learners can connect their theoretical knowledge to practical application in predictive maintenance tasks.• Equipping learners with a well-rounded skillset and emotional intelligence to handle challenging situations. <p>Interdisciplinary Teaching:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Incorporating interdisciplinary teaching methods that combine knowledge from various fields of	<p>through teamwork and common goals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Implementing AR gamification for knowledge delivery and engagement. <p>Expert Assistance and Emotional Connections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Providing learners with guidance from experts to develop niche skills required to become PM experts.• Implementing software that identifies individual emotional connections with the subject matter, enhancing engagement and understanding.	
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	<p>expertise to provide a holistic approach to predictive maintenance education.</p>		
<p>TN5: Developing interactive, modern and effective open educational resources (OERs) in PM that can be successfully delivered via online/blended education in innovative formats including augmented reality</p>	<p>Delivery of OERs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The implementation of Open Educational Resources (OERs) within academic programs, making educational materials freely accessible to students. <p>Increasing Training Attractiveness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efforts to enhance the appeal and desirability of training programs in predictive maintenance. <p>Raising Motivation Among Learners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategies and approaches aimed at boosting learner motivation within predictive maintenance education. 	<p>Open Source Software for Training Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilization of open-source software to develop training materials and resources for predictive maintenance education. <p>Availability of Specific AR/VR Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The presence of dedicated augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) technologies suitable for enhancing predictive maintenance training. <p>Augmented Reality (AR)/Virtual Reality (VR) Content Authoring Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tools and software used for creating content, modules, and applications in the AR and VR domains for educational purposes. <p>Online Personalized Teaching with VR/AR Enhancement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of online personalized teaching methods enriched with VR and AR applications to enhance the learning experience. <p>Lightweight AR Equipment:</p>	<p>Limited Budget:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constraints on financial resources available for developing and implementing predictive maintenance educational programs. <p>Limited Time:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constraints on the amount of time available for designing, delivering, and managing predictive maintenance training. <p>Content Creation and Maintenance Costs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs associated with developing, updating, and maintaining educational content and materials for predictive maintenance programs. <p>Integration Parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Factors and requirements that dictate how various components, technologies, and modules should be integrated into the educational system. <p>Seamless Integration of Natural Environment with Digital Systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ability to integrate digital technologies, such as augmented reality (AR) or virtual reality (VR), in a

	<p>Lack of Existing Up-to-Date OERs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges related to the availability of current and up-to-date open educational resources for predictive maintenance education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development and availability of lightweight or weightless AR equipment, ensuring ease of use and comfort for learners. <p>Tailored Content for Hardware and Field Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of educational content specifically designed to align with the hardware and practical field requirements of predictive maintenance education. 	<p>way that seamlessly blends with the real-world environment to provide an immersive learning experience.</p> <p>Without Loss of Reality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring that the integration of digital systems does not compromise the authenticity or real-life aspects of the learning experience.
<p>TN6: Ability to develop effective ethical learner analytics and online learner profile that will enable a better and more tailored educational service delivery complemented by a “student-centred” approach where learners are in charge of their own learning pathway</p>	<p>Diversity of Students:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The presence of students from various backgrounds, experiences, and skill levels in predictive maintenance education. <p>Need to Raise Motivation Among Students:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The importance of enhancing students' motivation to promote effective learning and provide an enriched educational experience. <p>Acquiring as Many Details as Possible During Student Enrollment Process:</p>	<p>AI to Personalize Learning Path and Pace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) to customize the learning journey and speed for each student based on their individual needs and capabilities. <p>Personalized Learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating a personalized learning experience tailored to each learner's preferences and requirements. <p>Predictive Analytics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilizing predictive analytics to anticipate learner needs and optimize the learning process. <p>Protocols for Usage of Learner Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing protocols and ethical guidelines for the collection and utilization of learner data to ensure data privacy and security. <p>AI for Profile Creation and Personalized Education Needs:</p>	<p>Restrictions in Use of User Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adhering to strict regulations and restrictions on the collection, storage, and utilization of user data, especially when it comes to sensitive personal information. <p>Data Privacy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring the privacy and security of learner data by implementing robust data protection measures, encryption, and compliance with privacy laws. <p>Different Legal Barriers for Using Learner Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigating through various legal barriers and regulations that vary across different regions and countries, which can impact the way learner data is handled. <p>Students' Denial to Disclose Certain Personal Information:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The process of gathering comprehensive information about students during enrollment while adhering to regulations governing the collection of personal data. <p>Market's Need for Work Efficiency Optimization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The demand in the job market for professionals who can contribute to optimizing work efficiency, which drives the importance of predictive maintenance education. <p>Profile Analysis of Potential Learners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The practice of analyzing the profiles of potential learners to identify their diverse needs, preferences, and requirements, aiming to create a student-	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Employing AI for the creation of learner profiles and to determine personalized educational needs, while maintaining ethical analytics practices. <p>Gradient and AI-Based Systems for Knowledge Measurement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Implementing gradient-based AI systems that can assess knowledge without hindering practical learning experiences. <p>Self-Evaluation and Progress Measurement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Encouraging self-evaluation both online and offline, measuring an individual's progress without comparing them to others. <p>Expert Team for Profile Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Assembling a team of experts to conduct profile analysis and seamlessly integrate it into the learning process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Facing challenges when students are unwilling to disclose certain personal information, leading to limitations in creating comprehensive learner profiles. <p>Learners' Lack of Awareness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Addressing the issue where learners may not always understand what they should learn and how the knowledge gained can be applicable in various real-world situations.
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	<p>centered educational experience.</p>		
<p>TN7: Ability to develop microcredential systems and skill validation/certification mechanisms that would improve the skill recognition of the learners</p>	<p>Overarching Microcredential System for PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing a comprehensive microcredentialing system designed specifically for PM professionals to recognize their skills and expertise. <p>Continuous Improvement and Lifelong Learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasizing the necessity for all PM professionals to engage in continuous improvement and lifelong learning to stay current with evolving technologies and industry best practices. <p>Limited Licenses Based on Microcredentials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introducing a system where professionals can earn limited licenses based on the number and types of microcredentials they 	<p>Integration of LMS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incorporating Learning Management Systems (LMS) into the educational infrastructure to facilitate the delivery of PM-related courses and training. <p>Blockchain Technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leveraging blockchain technologies to securely record and verify microcredentials and certifications earned by PM professionals, ensuring transparency and tamper-proof records. <p>Common EU Platforms for Validation/Certification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilizing existing common EU platforms that enable easier validation and certification of microcredentials, ensuring that these certifications are recognized and acceptable both within the European Union (EU) and globally. <p>Microcredentials Linked to Profiles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating a system where microcredentials earned by PM professionals are linked to their profiles, making it accessible to educational institutions and industrial bodies for verification and validation purposes. 	<p>Variety of Microcredential Systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognizing the existence of multiple microcredentialing systems and standards, making it important to establish a unified system that caters to the diverse needs of PM professionals. <p>European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The utilization of the ECTS system, which is widely recognized in European higher education, can provide a structured framework for the accumulation and transfer of learning credits within PM education programs. <p>Stigma Towards Blockchain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acknowledging that there may be a stigma associated with blockchain technology due to its association with cryptocurrencies, and addressing the need to educate stakeholders about its broader applications in secure credentialing. <p>Accreditation Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying the difficulties in accreditation systems and the reluctance of certain institutions to adopt new programs for accreditation and certification mechanisms,

	<p>acquire, allowing them to participate in specific levels of PM involvement.</p> <p>Universal Acceptance of Credentials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborating with relevant stakeholders to develop a certified system that ensures the skills acquired by learners through microcredentials are universally recognized and accepted. <p>Tailored Educational System:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognizing that the ideal PM job profile will require a more customized educational system that encompasses a broader range of skills and educational backgrounds. 	<p>Custom System for PM Needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing a customized system tailored to the unique requirements of the PM field to ensure that microcredentials and certifications align with industry-specific competencies. <p>Online Educational Platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing online educational platforms that not only provide PM training but also offer certification options, making it convenient for professionals to access learning resources and gain recognized credentials. 	<p>emphasizing the importance of flexible and adaptable accreditation processes.</p> <p>Increasing Industry Demand:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Noting the rising demand within the industry for PM professionals who possess portfolios and hands-on work experience rather than solely relying on academic qualifications.
<p>TN8: Ability of trainers to use existing infrastructures and resources offered by ongoing or past EU initiatives (i.e.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous exchange of PM professionals between academia and industry, promoting the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilizing open-source learning content to promote accessibility and affordability of educational resources in predictive maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges related to the lack of awareness among learners and professionals about existing educational and training resources in predictive maintenance.

<p>especially EIT KICs' Teaching Factory concept and their resource hubs).</p>	<p>integration of practical experience into education and training.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Leveraging existing resources, including industry collaborations, projects, and real-world applications, to enrich PM education and provide opportunities for hands-on learning.• Recognizing the importance of practical experience and hands-on skills development in PM, emphasizing the need for learners to engage in real-world projects.• Building a versatile infrastructure with various related projects to facilitate practical skill acquisition and provide a comprehensive learning experience.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Leveraging online platforms that facilitate the exchange of knowledge, collaboration among learners and professionals, and access to educational materials from diverse sources.• Integrating a combination of real and virtual environments, supported by various communication technologies, to create immersive and interactive learning experiences.• Ensuring the availability of equipment used in real-life scenarios for hands-on training and practical skill development.• Implementing AI tutoring systems, VR/AR training simulations, and blockchain technology to enhance learning outcomes, track students' progress securely, and provide a dynamic learning environment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Insufficient availability of resources, particularly in specialized domains or areas of study within predictive maintenance.• The importance of establishing clear selection criteria for choosing specific infrastructures and resources for training and education purposes.• The need for alignment between the provided infrastructures and resources and the actual training requirements and workplace needs in the field of predictive maintenance.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering awareness among learners and educational institutions about the availability of resources for PM education and training. • Developing skills to effectively utilize existing resources and opportunities for PM education. • Implementing strategies to lower costs associated with funding educational proposals and initiatives. 		
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Step 3: “Get down to earth” – imagine the realistic scenario in 10 years from now, how would realistically the PM trainer profile look like ? During the workshop fill in this table (moderator), the idea is to look at each skill, discuss its probability and maybe remove/add new ones.

Table 4.2 – Realistic scenario - Trainer Profile Use Case

Skill	Pressures that enable/push it	Technologies that enable/push it	Barriers
TN1: Limited know-how on adopting pedagogical and	Challenges in online education:	Components of UX Tracker: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning management systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of focus on mental health and motivation of learners.

<p>neuroscience strategies for boosting learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance and successfully embed them in digital formats (for online delivery in higher education and beyond)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Digital isolation of learners• Limited pay for educators• Limited career options for online instructors <p>Factors driving demand for online education:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Impact of COVID-19 pandemic• Increasing emphasis on student engagement and retention <p>Issues with traditional online teaching methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Loss of student interest with textbook lectures• Need for more interactive and engaging approaches <p>Importance of social learning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Helps students feel more connected to peers• Facilitates learning from each other's experiences <p>Strategies for enhancing social learning in online education:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Inclusion of discussion forums	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Video conferencing tools• Data analytics <p>Features of digital lesson format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Incorporation of gamification elements• Point collection and rewards system. <p>Utilization of wearable devices for students:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Tracking engagement and well-being• Providing personalized feedback and support	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Resistance to change among educators and their limited awareness about effective pedagogical strategies.• Need for extensive redesign of lecture formats to improve engagement and comprehension.• The value of real-life lessons in providing directness and enhanced learning experiences.• Challenges such as a lack of resources, time-consuming processes, and resistance from trainers when adopting new practices in education.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporation of group projects • Integration of other social learning activities 		
<p>TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online higher and vocational education (and beyond) and help educational institutions become more resilient while enabling companies to better motivate employees to engage in constant upskilling</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget allocation tied to student count, emphasizing the importance of enrollment and retention rates. • Emphasis on remote work and learning trends, highlighting the need for workforce upskilling and reskilling to adapt to changing job markets. • Development of expertise through a progressive set of certifications and incentives for continuous upskilling, leading to a more efficient workforce. • Concerns about social media addiction and the illusion of "easy living," indicating the need for digital literacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of AI-driven content recommendations on online learning platforms to enhance the relevance of learning materials. • Assignment of online personal tutors or consultants to each student for personalized support, encouragement, and addressing difficulties. • Utilization of online serious games for interactive and engaging learning experiences. • Implementation of adaptive learning technologies to customize the learning experience based on individual student needs, allowing them to learn at their own pace and in their preferred learning style. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A shift away from an exclusive focus on academic skills towards a greater emphasis on experiential learning. • Challenges related to access to reliable internet and devices, which can impede learning opportunities, especially in remote or underserved areas. • Lack of learner motivation, often due to societal needs and trends that lead to early termination of studies. • Variability in learners' knowledge and proficiency with digital systems, highlighting the importance of digital literacy education. • The influence of current social trends and social media, which often promote generic information and the perception of "easy" lives, potentially affecting learner priorities and motivation. • Issues such as limited access to technology and reliable internet connections, along with the challenge of balancing time and motivation due to work and family obligations.

	<p>and critical thinking skills in education.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing demand for lifelong learning, potentially supported by government or company-sponsored training programs to enhance workforce skills and adaptability. 		
<p>TN3: Better foster inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education in online deliveries in higher and vocational education and beyond</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of stricter rules and policies for diversity and inclusion in educational institutions and workplaces. • Recognition of diverse learning needs and accessibility requirements to ensure equal opportunities for all learners. • A focus on global inclusion and equality to create a more equitable and diverse learning and working environment. • The potential for increased workforce efficiency as a result of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of accessible technology, including the use of assistive technologies and adaptive learning platforms to support learners with disabilities and diverse needs. • The need for improved connectivity in remote locations to ensure equal access to educational platforms and their accessibility features. • The development of customized interactive digital systems that consider an individual's unique personality assets and build upon them to enhance their learning experience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget limitations impacting the development and implementation of accessible features in educational technology, exacerbating the digital divide. • Challenges related to remote location infrastructure and a shortage of trained experts to serve as online personal tutors for all learners. • The absence of personalized education systems due to the significant diversification of society, making it difficult to cater to the unique needs and preferences of every learner.

	<p>diverse perspectives, skills, and backgrounds contributing to problem-solving and innovation.</p>		
<p>TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections, creation emotional responses to improve learning, and understanding timing (for learning content delivery)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pressure on educational institutions to retain students in their programs due to competition in the education sector. • The significance of research in neuroscience and psychology, with a focus on developing emotional intelligence skills in learners. • The need for practical application of knowledge and the cultivation of problem-solving abilities. • The use of group assignments and collaboration as training for future workplace scenarios, emphasizing teamwork 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of UX research to enhance the user experience in educational technology and platforms. • The utilization of virtual reality (VR) for immersive learning experiences and AI-driven emotional analytics to gauge and respond to learners' emotional states. • Digital interactive courses featuring real-life problem-solving exercises and enriched with various multimedia elements such as videos, animations, and VR/AR examples. • Collaboration with experts from the educational sector to transform content and delivery methods to develop learners' intelligence effectively. • The implementation of adaptive learning technology to customize learning content and activities based 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical concerns about emotional manipulation in the context of advanced technology and educational content, raising questions about the responsible use of emotional analytics. • High costs associated with the implementation of advanced technology in education, which can strain budgets. • The complexity of course design and implementation, highlighting the need for well-structured and well-coordinated efforts. • The growth of the content development team, requiring effective coordination among various stakeholders to ensure a comprehensive and balanced final outcome. • The insufficient amount of research conducted on the subject, emphasizing the need for further research to inform and improve

	<p>and communication skills.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A shift in education towards fostering a deep understanding of the subject matter and the consequences of actions, rather than rote memorization and robotic responses. • The importance of adapting quickly to challenges in the fast-paced technological landscape, preparing learners to be flexible and responsive to change. 	<p>on each individual learner's needs and interests.</p>	<p>educational practices and technology integration.</p>
<p>TN5: Developing interactive, modern and effective open educational resources (OERs) in PM that can be successfully delivered via online/blended education in innovative formats including augmented reality</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress in the creation and dissemination of OERs, which are openly accessible and often free educational resources. • Growing demand for flexible and accessible learning materials that can cater to a wide range of learners. • The need for easy, free, and unlimited access to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of instructional design software for creating effective and engaging educational content. • Utilizing augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) for interactive educational content, along with content creation platforms to support these technologies. • The importance of access to a centralized educational platform that offers online education while also facilitating the integration of AR and VR applications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reservations or concerns regarding the use of augmented reality in educational settings, potentially stemming from uncertainty or skepticism about its effectiveness. • Limited funding available for content development, which can hinder the creation of AR-based educational materials. • The complexity and associated costs of implementing AR technologies in education, including hardware, software, and training.

	<p>educational materials, particularly to meet the increasing demand for Project Management (PM) experts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligning learning activities with market trends, ensuring that educational content addresses current and emerging needs in various fields, including Project Management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The availability of technology, both in terms of hardware and software tools, for the development of specialized educational content, highlighting the readiness of the technology for educational applications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The substantial development work required to tailor AR applications to specific educational fields, which can be costly and may necessitate support from subject matter experts to ensure realism and relevance.
<p>TN6: Ability to develop effective ethical learner analytics and online learner profile that will enable a better and more tailored educational service delivery complemented by a “student-centred” approach where learners are in charge of their own learning pathway</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The importance of recognizing the diversity of students, including their varied backgrounds, skills, and future goals. The shift towards learner-centered education, emphasizing personalized learning experiences that cater to individual student needs. The use of questionnaires to create comprehensive student profiles, which can include skill levels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The importance of personalizing educational platforms to cater to individual student needs and preferences. The use of learning analytics platforms and data privacy solutions to collect and analyze student data while safeguarding their personal information. Profiling data fed into machine learning (ML) algorithms to generate personalized course development pathways for each student, all while maintaining strict personal data safety standards. The need to follow best practices established in similar systems in various domains, with a preference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Budget considerations in developing and maintaining educational systems that prioritize data privacy and security. Concerns surrounding data privacy and security, with particular attention to the challenges of complying with regulations governing the handling and usage of personal information. The complexity of the task, wherein system developers must thoroughly understand learner profiles and strive to accommodate the most representative and diverse cases to create effective and compliant educational solutions.

	<p>and future plans, to better tailor educational experiences to each student.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The potential benefits of a student-centered approach, where learners feel that the educational system is designed to meet their needs and support their understanding of challenging subjects. 	<p>for technical expertise and proven approaches to ensure the successful development of personalized educational platforms.</p>	
<p>TN7: Ability to develop microcredential systems and skill validation/certification mechanisms that would improve the skill recognition of the learners</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employers and universities have specific requirements for the competencies and skills they expect from learners and graduates. • The job market experiences rapid changes in demands, necessitating continuous learning and adaptation by both learners and professionals. • The need for workforce competencies verification, especially 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The development of detailed online profiles that include information on education qualifications, skills, and work experience, providing a comprehensive view of an individual's qualifications. • The potential utilization of existing common EU platforms that enable easier validation and certification, making it more widely accepted within the EU and potentially on a global scale. • The availability of online certification platforms that can be used to host content without the need to build a new platform from scratch, streamlining the process of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges with non-cohesive credentials in the field, where qualifications and certifications lack standardization and coherence. • A lack of awareness about existing platforms that offer acceptable microcredentials, hindering their recognition and use. • Resistance to accepting microcredentials as a valuable certification method, potentially due to skepticism or unfamiliarity with this relatively new form of credentialing. • The importance of achieving wide acceptance of microcredentials in the education and job markets. • Designing exams and assessments to ensure that learners possess skills that

	<p>for various positions and at different skill levels, to ensure that candidates meet specific job requirements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The potential for learners to be motivated to acquire certifications that demonstrate their skills, making them more attractive to potential employers who can be assured of their capabilities at a known level. 	<p>creating and sharing credentials and qualifications.</p>	<p>are relevant and in demand in the job market.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need for cooperation with employers while striking a balance with educational perspectives, aligning the skills acquired with the demands of the job market to ensure graduates are job-ready.
<p>TN8: Ability of trainers to use existing infrastructures and resources offered by ongoing or past EU initiatives (i.e. especially EIT KICs' Teaching Factory concept and their resource hubs).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The presence of a large quantity of EU initiatives in the education sector, highlighting a diverse range of projects and programs. Opportunities for collaboration among educational institutions, leveraging shared resources and expertise to enhance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need for an open platform that allows users to search for and identify overlaps or complementary aspects among various EU initiatives. The use of online collaboration tools and resource sharing platforms to facilitate cooperation and resource sharing among different initiatives. The importance of video-conferencing software and a curated selection of instructional videos, animations, and VR/AR content to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The existence of closed systems or initiatives that are not open to collaboration, hindering cooperation and synergy with other programs. Resistance to collaboration and a lack of alignment with existing systems or structures, which can impede the effectiveness of initiatives. Bureaucratic hurdles and licensing issues that can complicate the implementation and adoption of EU initiatives. The absence of coordination, continuation, and documentation,

	<p>the quality of education.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Collaboration between educational institutions and industry partners to bridge the gap between academic learning and practical skills required in the workforce.• The importance of developing training infrastructure and accessible learning materials, which can be made available as resources even after project completion.• The need for greater governmental support to encourage trainers and educators to utilize EU initiatives, particularly due to the increased demand for skills development and workforce preparation.	<p>support remote learning and collaboration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The availability of content management systems to store and organize educational content, ensuring smooth access and utilization.• The necessity of operational equipment and manufacturer support packages to ensure uninterrupted operation of educational technology.• Leveraging online technologies to tailor available resources to current educational needs and adapt to evolving requirements.• The significance of high-speed network technologies that enable trainers to use VR, AR, and AI-powered learning tools in real time, even when students are located remotely.	<p>which often renders the outcomes of projects unusable for future purposes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Limited public awareness of many EU initiatives, along with private companies' preference for their own resources or training initiatives.• Inequitable access to resources due to geographical constraints or availability limited to specific organizations or individuals, potentially contributing to disparities in education and training opportunities.
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3. TASK ALLOCATION

Partner	PM Workforce Workshop	PM Trainer Workshop
CERTH + UPI (jointly or split)	✓	✓
YET		✓
ATC	✓	
HELIX		✓
ISIM + INTELIFORM (jointly)	✓	✓
EITM	✓	✓
MUB		✓
LCC	✓	
DB	✓	

PreMETS

D2.1 Future Employee Profile

ACC	✓	
WEG		✓

4. APPENDIX

4.1 Appendix – Information Sheet & Consent Form

The general objectives of PreMETS are to introduce an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training for the development of a coherent digital platform that covers all aspects of the PM training process:

- Fostering new, innovative and multidisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning in the field of PM by introducing an innovatively co-created PM curriculum (covering green, digital, entrepreneurial and resilience skills for PM) complemented by innovative teaching methods (i.e. EIT Manufacturing's Teaching Factory Concept), micro-credential certification and bespoke digital learning and co-creation platform for upskilling the current and future PM workforce and tackling skill gaps and mis-matches via skill forecasting and policy making.
- Helping PM companies and related service provider SMEs achieve corporate social responsibility by directly impacting on reducing environmental damage, diminishing social and societal risks and boosting their revenues.
- Stimulating a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial attitudes with regards to achieving resilient PM solutions, mind-sets and skills in adult, vocational and higher education learners.
- Facilitating the flow and co-creation of PM knowledge between higher education, VET actors, research, the public sector and the business sector in the field of PM in order to jointly contribute to upskilling and regional economic growth by developing capacities and clusters in the field of PM.
- Building and supporting effective and efficient PM higher education and vocational education and training systems delivered via a joint digital platform, which enables connectivity and inclusivity, contributing to innovation and equal access to high quality education for all in the emerging work field of PM.

To ensure that the training needs of both future employee in PM and future trainers in PM are fully reflected in the educational content, PreMETS adopts an innovative approach as a starting point of its methodological development by relying on OECD's strategic foresight approach. The futuring/foresight process is linked with the pre-identified training needs for PM workforce and PM trainer needs. After the foresight is finalized, the learner & trainer profiles will be based on use-case approaches.

You are kindly invited to take part in one of our skills foresight workshop which will last up to 1.5h.

If you give your consent, the skills foresight workshop (or part of it) will be video/audio recorded and images will be taken throughout the activity. Part of the recordings/videos will be used by the PreMETS Consortium for dissemination and for the creation of the Skills Analysis Report.

Please read the information and sign the following box

- I have been informed about the PreMETS project and the present Skills Foresight Workshop and I have understood what the discussion is about and what it aims to achieve.
- I was allowed sufficient time to consider whether to give my consent and was also given the opportunity to ask questions. Any questions I asked were answered to my satisfaction.
- I am aware that my participation is entirely voluntary and that I may withdraw my consent at any time without giving a reason.
- I understand that I may choose not to answer any of the questions that I will be asked. During the workshops, or at its end, I can ask to modify or remove some of my remarks.
- I understand that the information provided during the workshops, (other than personal information that may identify me) may be used for reports, publications, dissemination and other scientific / research purposes.
- I understand that my participation will be completely anonymous and I will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications.
- I understand that my personal details, such as name and contact details, will not be published or disclosed to anyone.
- I am aware/have been informed that any personal details will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the data protection policy of the organizer.
- I authorize the recording of these Policy Lab workshops and understand that it will be used by the project's consortium for dissemination and reporting purposes according to the GDPR principles.

Name of the Participant:

Place & Date:

Signature: